

Control of *Chlamydia abortus* infections in livestock

Chlamydia abortus is an intracellular gram-negative bacterium with a broad host range, including domestic ruminants, pigs, horses and wildlife, although sheep and goats are the main affected host species.

The pathogen is responsible for the disease **ovine chlamydiosis (aka enzootic abortion of ewes and ovine enzootic abortion)**, which has a worldwide distribution. It is one of the major causes of foetal death *in utero*, resulting in the delivery of dead lambs and kids in late gestation (last 1-3 weeks). The pathogen and disease is principally spread through an oro-nasal route and only affects pregnant animals. The pathogen is also zoonotic and so can also cause disease in humans, principally pregnant women resulting in spontaneous abortion or miscarriage.

Infected cell full of *C. abortus* bacteria

Disease can be controlled through a combination of diagnostic testing and vaccination. Also early intervention to remove infected products of abortion, disinfect and separate the affected animals is critical to reducing transmission. However, diagnostic tests are currently laboratory based, so there is a need to develop rapid penside tests.

Live and inactivated vaccines are available but there are issues with safety and length of immunity.

We have developed a vaccine based on the outer membrane proteins (image on left) of the bacterium (COMC) but is complex to produce. We have also identified the individual COMC proteins that will allow us to develop a vaccine that distinguishes infected from vaccinated animals (DIVA).

REPRODIVAC Aims

- To refine the manufacture of the newly developed safer (non-zoonotic) COMC vaccine
- To develop a recombinant antigen DIVA-compatible vaccine based on COMC proteins
- To develop companion DIVA-compatible diagnostic tests to rapidly identify infections penside so that appropriate disease management strategies can be put in place.